

Best Practices and Guidelines for Cybersecurity Training

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Abstract

Cybersecurity has never been more important than today. While increasing digitalization brings many advantages, it also comes with increased risks of cyberattacks: A growing attack surface contributes to a higher probability of attacks, and increasing dependence on digital systems and services contribute to higher consequences of attacks when they are successful. On top of this, the geopolitical situation has also led to an increased activity among many different threat actors, including cyber criminals, nation states and cyber activists. One of the main challenges to combat the cyber threat is the lack of skilled people: Not only are we missing around 4 mio. cybersecurity professionals on a global scale: We also have a huge challenge of ensuring that the general public, and in particular those working with IT, have a strong knowledge of cybersecurity. This need for training is also addressed in new regulations, such as the NIS2 Directive in the European Union. In this paper, we define 20 principles for good cybersecurity training, with a particular focus on technical training that goes beyond awareness. The principles are based on a combination of theoretical knowledge, practical experience, and extensive dialogues with stakeholders from both industry and academia through joint trainings and workshops. The paper explores topics such as active learning, combination of theory and practice through hands-on exercises, collaborative learning, gamification with clear missions, scaffolding and the use of hints and real-world context and experience. We believe that the paper can serve as an important reference for development of trainings, training platforms and courses in cybersecurity. We also believe the methodology with collaboration across companies and academia can contribute to increase the quality of trainings, and eventually contribute to closing the cybersecurity skills gap.

Keywords: Active Learning; Cybersecurity; Innovation.

1 Introduction

The cyber threat against our societies, including individuals, companies, and government organisations, is higher than ever before. There is not a single reason behind this, yet some of the drivers are increasing digitalization which leads to both larger attack surfaces (thus increasing the probability of attacks) and a higher dependability on our IT infrastructure (increasing the consequences of attacks) as well as geopolitical changes that has led to an increase in both cyber activism and cyber espionage. One could also speculate that the geopolitical changes during the last 5-10 years might have given cyber criminals new opportunities with less probability of being prosecuted. In a Danish context, the governmental agency Centre for Cybersecurity has assessed the threats of both cyber espionage and cybercrime against Denmark as very high, the threat of cyber activism against Denmark as high, and the threat of destructive cyber attacks against Denmark as medium (CFCS, 2024). The picture is similar in most other European countries, and also on a global scale the challenges of cybercrime keep growing with the losses increasing every year (IC3, 2025).

One of the biggest challenges is the lack of competences. On a global scale, the 2024 ISC2 Cybersecurity Workforce Study (ISC2, 2024) estimates a global gap of 4,762,963 persons, an increase of 19,1% compared to the year before. On top of this comes a need to upskill the many people working with IT and digitalization: They might not need to become cybersecurity professionals, but they need a high level of knowledge to build,

maintain and operate systems in a secure manner. New legislation such as the NIS2 directive from the European Union is expected to increase the need for cyber competences even more.

Cyber ranges and cybersecurity training platforms (Kjorveziroski et al., 2020; Darwish et al., 2020) is a popular basis for making cybersecurity training active and engaging (Russo et al., 2023). These platforms usually provide virtual environments, where the learners get hands-on experiences in a closed and secure environment, often combined with gamification (Mahmoud et al., 2024). The objective of this paper is two-fold: We would like to spark a discussion about good cybersecurity training that goes “beyond awareness”, and we would like the paper to serve as a source for everyone developing and implementing cybersecurity training. The paper is based on a joint project supported by NCC-DK, the Denmark Cybersecurity Coordination Centre (NCC-DK, 2025) (co-funded by the European Union), where three companies that all work with cybersecurity training based on different platforms have joined forces to develop joint best-practice guidelines and principles for cybersecurity training. Campfire Security ApS is a spin-out from Aalborg University and based on a further development of the Haaukins platform (Panum et al., 2019), which provides training based on challenges in a format known as Capture The Flag. SagaLabs ApS is developing scenario based training, and is a spinout from the Danish Association of Cyber Alumni, i.e. former cyber conscripts. The initial platform and the name was inspired by Erhvervsakademi Aarhus, a Danish educational institution. Finally, ICSRange ApS is developing training specifically focusing on industrial systems and OT (Operational Technology). While the trainings share many characteristics, i.e. the use of virtual environments, active learning and gamification, both the platforms and the context in which they are used differ. In addition to the companies, the non-profit association Dansk IT is also participating in the project. Dansk IT is a central player for IT professionals in Denmark and works to promote the role of IT in both society and business. As an independent interest organization, Dansk IT brings together members with a common desire to strengthen professionalism, drive digital development and ensure responsible use of technology. For this project in particular, the organisation includes a large share of the Danish cybersecurity community. This paper is motivated by the desire to learn from each other and from the theory in order to enable the educational and cybersecurity community to provide even better trainings.

2 Methodology

The 20 principles in this paper have been developed throughout 2024 and 2025, based on a number of sources and activities:

- Scientific literature, including that listed in Section 1 of this paper.
- Practical experience by the authors of this paper. The authors represent three different platforms as also described in Section 1, and therefore experiences with different learning needs, methods and target groups. In the context of this paper, 8 jointly arranged training events were held, where participants used one or more different platforms, and the authors observed the use and afterwards discussed and evaluated points to include as joint principles. After each training, an oral evaluation was done with the participants, who also provided inputs to the discussions and thus the principles. Most of the events were open so anybody could attend and attracted a variety of mainly IT professionals – both technical profiles such as developers/programmers and less technical profiles such as IT architects and managers. These events included the following examples, each making use of two different platforms:
 - On November 6, 2024, we did a 4-hour evening event with focus on security of Operational Technology. The first part of the event focused on learning techniques and practical tools, whereas the second part was scenario based: In a virtual environment, the participants were tasked with a mission of hindering an enemy fleet in leaving the harbours. The scenario was called “Operation Northern Shield”.

- On March 6, 2025, we did a full day event with hands-on introduction to cybersecurity, targeting all IT professionals. The morning part of the workshop was focusing on hands-on cybersecurity fundamentals in a Capture-The-Flag format, where the participants should solve challenges in virtual labs, and where each challenge would result in points. In the afternoon, the participants should apply the tools and techniques from the morning in a realistic scenario, "Operation Hidden Spice", in a threat-hunting mission, where the task is to confirm or refuse the suspicion that an employee may have acted as an insider.
- A total of 4 workshops were held, which were open to the public and mainly attended by people from the Danish cybersecurity community, with the aim of discussing the principles. They were usually attended by a smaller group of 5 externals, but included both people with technical and didactical backgrounds, and led to changes, adjustments, and additions of new principles. The workshops mainly focused on discussing two documents:
 - The Best Practices and Guidelines for cybersecurity training as outlined in this paper.
 - Ways of measuring and quantifying cybersecurity competences achieved during trainings, e.g. using the NICE framework (NICE, 2025) and the Dreyfuss model (Rousse & Dreyfus, 2021).

During the iterations of practical experiences and workshops, the number of principles grew from 10 to 20.

In the following, we will present the principles that we have agreed upon. The principles are structured so that each principle contains both motivations, descriptions and at least one example. The point of adding examples to all principles was actually a result of one of the workshops, since this increases the clarity and understanding even when the principles are applied by different target groups.

3 About the principles

When defining the principles, it is important to keep in mind that the overall goal of the principles is to provide common best practices and guidelines for cybersecurity training. It is established as part of a collaborative project within the cybersecurity training sector in Denmark and supported by NCC. The guidelines are not meant as a checklist to follow, but rather a set of best practices and guidelines to consider when designing cybersecurity training. Not all practices/guidelines are relevant for all aspects of cybersecurity training, and there can also be valid reasons for making different choices.

In our context, we are mainly covering cybersecurity training for IT professionals, including software and security professionals. We do not aim to cover e.g. standard awareness training for non-IT employees, but focus on trainings that provides the learners with skills and/or competences in addition to naturally raising awareness.

Finally, the principles are designed to be constantly developed based on continuously collecting inputs and experiences from relevant stakeholders.

4 The principles

This section presents the 20 principles.

In the descriptions, we sometimes refer to "challenges", which in this context means specific security-related puzzles or problems the learners must solve, and "flags", which in this context is usually a small text string that serves as a proof of completing a challenge.

4.1 Explain the purpose

To make sure the learners are motivated and see the value in the training, it is crucial to explain the purpose from the beginning: Why is this training important for them (and/or their company), what will they learn, and

how will it help them? For example, a person in the management role could learn about basic cyber attack techniques to (1) gain a better understanding of the cyber threat and (2) learn the terminology to communicate with more technical IT people – and eventually be able to collaborate across the organization to be better at preventing, detecting, responding to and recovering from cyber attacks.

4.2 Explain the teaching methodology

A common question from learners is: “Why do we have to do this?”. It is always recommended to explain why you have designed the learning experience as you have. When using gamification and challenges, it is particularly important that the learning goals are clear when developing the challenges, and that the learning goals and context is also clear for the learner – it might be fun, but it should be clear for the learning that it is more than that. For example, when learning how a dictionary attack works on a password login, the point is not to master dictionary attacks, but to understand how to create better password policies.

4.3 Active Learning

Training should be based on active learning, rather than simply reading materials or watching videos. Active learning not only improves retention and learning outcomes, but it is also more engaging and fun for the learners. Active learning can take many shapes and forms: Exercises, competitions, discussion sessions, and much more. (Prümmer, van Steen and van den Berg, 2024) recently conducted a systematic review of current cybersecurity training methods and identified seven distinct training methods: Game-based training, presentation-based training, simulation-based training, information-based training, video-based training and text-based training (while also mentioning punishment-based training). While most of these can have active learning elements, our experience is that active learning often evolves around discussions, cases (can focus on human, organizational or technical aspects or a mix of these), gamification, and/or use of formats such as Capture The Flag or other kind of virtual lab scenarios. The latter are widely used in the industry, e.g. HackTheBox (Hack The Box, 2025), Try Hack Me (TryHackMe, 2025), as well as by the companies of the authors (Campfire Security ApS, SagaLabs ApS and ICSRange ApS), and the basic idea is that the learner can get hands-on experience with security/hacking in a closed and secure environment – often based on getting points or succeeding in missions, which together with the resemblance of real situations is very motivating.

4.4 Taking into account different learning styles

There are different theories on learning styles, but the short summary is that different people learn best in different ways. This is something that should always be considered when designing learning materials. One model is that of Neil Fleming: The VAR/VARK model (Fleming, 2001), which include four sensory modalities, i.e. visual learning, aural learning, reading/writing learning and kinesthetic learning – while also emphasizing that people might prefer a mix of these. When creating training materials, it is recommended to ensure that as many learning preferences as possible are accommodated - ideally by having some redundancy. For example, making sure that the same concept is explained both visually, by text and by practical assignments.

4.5 Use a well-known framework for measuring learning outcomes

Academia often uses taxonomies such as Blooms taxonomy, which refers to knowledge, skills and competences. While this can be hard to use for shorter trainings – measured in hours or days rather than in months or years – it is recommended to use a well-known framework for formulating learning outcomes – for example the NICE framework (NICE, 2025), or variations of it.

4.6 Role based training – and also collaboration across roles

Training should be designed according to people's different roles, so that the training is both relevant and fit the backgrounds of the learners and the challenges they experience. When working in teams during a training session or a course, the experience should ideally be designed so that people with different roles need to work together – this supports not only team building, but also the ability to collaborate across roles. For example, a challenge could require network knowledge to do network scanning and find a vulnerable service, whereas programming skills would be required to either exploit or patch the vulnerability. There is also a need for thinking across attack (red) and defense (blue) – as to master one side, you also need to understand the other. For this reason, platforms and courses should be designed to train for both sides. This aspect is also underlined in both the NIS2 directive, and in the European Cybersecurity Skills framework (ENISA, 2022).

4.7 Combining theory and practice

The best learning happens when theory and practice is combined, and in general we recommend breaking down the learning blocks in small parts: It of course depends on topics, but in general it is good to have practical/hands-on problems, experiments or cases every time a new tool, concept or method is introduced. This reinforces the learning of this new tool/concept/method and makes the learner ready to build further knowledge on top. People learn differently and have different preferences in terms of learning styles, so the exact pattern and mix of theory and practice will always depend on the individual. An example could be to build training paths with components, where each component contains (1) introduction/theory, (2) practical challenge and (3) reflection/feedback.

4.8 One thing at a time

For many learners who are new to cybersecurity, the initial learning steps can be overwhelming with many words, methods, concepts, and tools. Add on top that the learners also might need to accustom themselves to a new platform, including how to access the materials, different kind of cyber ranges or virtual labs, and point/scoring systems. We recommend that material is designed with this observation in mind, so the learning curve becomes manageable. On the other hand, it is also important that the learners feel they are learning something new: Therefore, it is recommended to think outside the "usual toolbox". An example of an easy learning curve could be that the first challenge is merely to insert a flag given in the challenge description, the next is to find a flag on a simple website, and the next again to solve a simple challenge that does not require any tools. Thus, the learner will learn a small new step for every challenge and based on this be able to solve more advanced tasks.

4.9 Ease of use

A learning platform or a cyber range should be easy and intuitive to use for the learner. This means that it should be simple for inexperienced users to access resources and navigate the platform or cyber range. If platforms become too unpolished or too complex, the learner may use more energy navigating the platform or cyber range, rather than obtaining the skills and knowledge planned. For example, it should be intuitive which steps to follow for a beginner – especially if the training is without (much) supervision.

4.10 ChatGPT (and other LLMs) safe challenges

ChatGPT and other Large Language Models are amazing for many purposes – including for learning. However, challenges and exercises need to be "GPT Safe" in the sense that they should not be solvable by merely providing the challenge description. It can be just too hard for learners to resist from cheating when easy points are in sight.

4.11 Collaborative learning

Learning together is always a great way of learning: Instead of solving exercises and problems alone, it is recommended to let learners work together. This often leads to good discussions which support the learning process, and situations where learners are helping each other is also good learning for all parties involved. Compared to working individually, it decreases the risk of being stuck and increases motivation and fun for the learner. As a bonus, learners get to know each other better. For most tasks, we recommend working in smaller groups of 2-4 learners, but this depends of course on the tasks at hand. Another way to motivate for collaborative learning would be to give an option of earning badges by helping others.

4.12 Gamification with a clear mission

Gamification is often setup as solving problems and getting points – or in the cybersecurity world to solve challenges and get flags – which then give points. This often works well, and it is impressive to see how much engagement and motivation gamification creates. However, the effects of gamification can be further boosted by working with missions and storylines instead of “just” getting flags or points. For example, building a storyline of infiltrating a malicious actor through their website might be more engaging for the learners than to simply find a website vulnerability (even though the actual task is the same). This principle is not to make the tasks more complex or less explained, but to build the right storylines where the goals are larger than simply getting a flag.

4.13 Clearly described tasks

In the cybersecurity community, there are many implicit understandings. When training people outside of this specific community, it is easy to get lost. A description of an exercise, where the learners were supposed to exploit a samba vulnerability, gain access to a server, and find a file on that server with the name flag.txt, once had the description “Have you ever tried dancing samba? Neither have we, but it might come in handy here”. With this, the learner would have no clue where to start and what to achieve. It might be a fun description for a CTF competition, where part of the competition is to decode that specific language, but it is not suitable in a training context. This principle depends a bit on how supervised the learners are: The more they are expected to work independently, the more important it is that descriptions are clear. It is important to explain “implicit” terminology, like 0-day, SIEM etc. – at least it should always be carefully considered to write out abbreviations in full.

4.14 Hints are important

While some level of frustration is okay, it is important not to be completely blocked without any possibility to advance. That is why hints are important. On the other hand, there is also a lot of learning in figuring things out, and much satisfaction in succeeding with this. This makes it non-trivial to provide the right hints – also, it can be difficult to automatize, since the hints ideally are depending on the individual learner (or group of learners) and their progress. AI and the use of Large Language Models is something that should be considered in this context, as it might be an efficient and scalable way to provide context-based hints.

4.15 A proper debrief

After finishing a course or learning lecture it is important to debrief and go through the learnings. This helps the learner retain what is learned. It is also a good opportunity to collect feedback for future improvements. Examples of debrief questions could be: What were the most important learnings for you from this course? Which new skills did you acquire? How can what you learned be applied in your everyday life, personally and professionally?

4.16 Making achievements visible

It is also important to equip the learners with visible proofs of their achievements such as certificates and/or badges. Not only does it give the user a more satisfactory experience, it also provides a valuable recognition for external purposes, and can be used on e.g. social media and in CVs.

4.17 Taking into account self-efficacy

Self-efficacy is a person's belief in their ability to perform a task or achieve a goal, and plays an important role for both performance and motivation. Some people might start out with a low self-efficacy, making it important to give them positive experiences with their own achievements from the beginning. And for those starting out with a high self-efficacy, it is also important that they can accomplish their expectations. In general, it is just important that the learners can complete the tasks they start out with, instead of being stuck. A particular consequence is that mechanisms should be in place to help everybody starting out at the right level. Also, this is related to having a hint system, so people are not being stuck.

4.18 Real-world context and experience

Design training scenarios based on real-world cybersecurity threats and use cases, using current trends such as ransomware, supply chain attack, and cloud security challenges. This should help the student gain familiarity with concepts that are applicable to real threats. Ideally, the scenarios are as close to the everyday life of the learners as possible – including the use of same or similar systems, software and operating systems.

4.19 Training for the challenges of tomorrow

Cybersecurity is moving fast forward, and threats and challenges evolve. It is important that trainings are updated, and that new trends are quickly incorporated into the training materials. For example, as LLM's have become more common place a new type of attack has appeared called "Training Data Poisoning". Even though this is a new concept, at the time of writing, it should be incorporated into the learning, so learners understand the underlying rules and dangers of the attack.

4.20 Training for incidents

Much training is focused on prevention and detection of cyber-attacks. However, it is equally important also to train for incident management (including both respond and recover), which makes it important to include aspects such as responsibilities, crisis management, communications and human burnouts.

5 Discussion

The principles we have presented have been defined mainly in collaboration between companies and a variety of stakeholders, including the potential learners. There is also an academic involvement, since one of the authors is active in both academia and in one of the involved companies. We believe that the combination of collaboration across companies, academia and other stakeholders to define best practices through exercises and workshops is interesting and valuable: Making efficient and engaging cybersecurity training is simply in everyone's interest. While we believe that community contributions to the body of knowledge is important, we also acknowledge that there are potential commercial interests when involving companies in research like this. As the principles are essentially a synthesis of existing knowledge, experiences, observations and discussions, we would like to further explore how they can be more systematically validated. This could be through larger use studies. The work of the paper has also made it clear that there are many different contexts, settings and goals when it comes to cybersecurity training. Not all principles apply to all situations, and as such they should not be used as a completely check-list of must-do requirements.

6 Conclusion

The lack of cybersecurity competences is one of the biggest challenges when it comes to combating the increasing cybersecurity threats. To address this challenge, there is a strong need for cybersecurity training at all levels – from awareness training for everybody to specialized training for cybersecurity experts and professionals. In this paper, we mainly address the needs for training of IT professionals.

The paper presents 20 principles for cybersecurity training, which reflect good practices. The principles are based on a combination of theoretical knowledge, practical experience, and extensive dialogues with stakeholders from both industry and academia through a number of joint trainings and workshops. We hope that the principles can inspire further dialogue and discussions, and that they also can be used as inspiration for the many organisations working with cybersecurity training.

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References

- CFCS (2024) The Cyber Threat Against Denmark, 2024 edition. Centre for CyberSecurity, Available at: <https://www.cfcs.dk/en/cybertruslen/threat-assessments/the-cyber-threat-against-denmark/>. (Accessed June 4, 2025)
- Darwish, O., Stone, C. M., Karajeh, O., & Alsinglawi, B. (2020). Survey of educational cyber ranges. Paper presented at the Web, Artificial Intelligence and Network Applications: Proceedings of the Workshops of the 34th International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications (WAINA-2020), 1037-1045.
- ENISA (2022). European Cybersecurity Skills Framework Role Profiles (<https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/european-cybersecurity-skills-framework-role-profiles>)
- Fleming, N. D. (2001). Teaching and learning styles : VARK strategies. ISBN 10:0473079569, ISBN 13:9780473079567.
- Hack The Box (2025). Hack The Box, <https://hackthebox.com>. (Accessed June 3, 2025).
- IC3 (2025) Internet Crime Report 2024. Federal Bureau of Investigation, Internet Crime Complaint Center. Available at: https://www.ic3.gov/AnnualReport/Reports/2024_IC3Report.pdf.
- ISC2 (2024) 2024 Cybersecurity Workforce Study. Available at <https://www.isc2.org/Insights/2024/10/ISC2-2024-Cybersecurity-Workforce-Study>.
- Kjorveziroski, V., Mishev, A., Filiposka, S. (2020). Cybersecurity Training Platforms Assessment. In: Dimitrova, V., Dimitrovski, I. (eds) ICT Innovations 2020. Machine Learning and Applications. 12th International Conference, ICT Innovations 2020. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 1316. Springer, Cham. https://doi-org.zorac.aub.aau.dk/10.1007/978-3-030-62098-1_15
- Mahmoud, R. V., Anagnostopoulos, M., & Pedersen, J. M. (2024). Active Learning and Cybersecurity Training: Best practices and recommendations on using Cyber Ranges. International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education, 14, 131-139. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060908>.
- NICE (2025), NICE Framework Resource Center, NIST National Institute of Standards and Technology. Available at <https://www.nist.gov/itl/applied-cybersecurity/nice/nice-framework-resource-center> (Accessed June 4, 2025).
- NCC-DK (2025), Denmark Cybersecurity Coordination Centre, <https://ncc-dk.dk>.
- Panum, T. K., Hageman, K. D., Pedersen, J. M., & Hansen, R. R. (2019). Haaukins: A Highly Accessible and Automated Virtualization Platform for Security Education. I M. Chang, D. G. Sampson, R. Huang, A. S. Gomes, N-S. Chen, I. I. Bittencourt, K. Kinshuk, D. Dermeval, & I. M. Bittencourt (red.), 2019 IEEE 19th International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies (ICALT) (s. 236-238). [8820918] IEEE. International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies (ICALT) <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICALT.2019.00073>
- Prümmer, J., van Steen, T. and van den Berg, B., 2024. A systematic review of current cybersecurity training methods. Computers & Security, 136, p.103585.
- Rousse, B. S., & Dreyfus, S. E. (2021). Revisiting the six stages of skill acquisition. In E. M. Silva Mangiante, K. Peno, & J. Northup (Eds.), Teaching and learning for adult skill acquisition: Applying the Dreyfus and Dreyfus model in different fields (pp. 3–27). Charlotte, NC: Information Age Publishing, Inc.
- Russo, E., Ribaudo, M., Orlich, A., Longo, G., and Armando, A. 2023. Cyber Range and Cyber Defense Exercises: Gamification Meets University Students. In Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Gamification in Software Development, Verification, and Validation (Gamify 2023). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3617553.3617888>
- Try Hack Me (2025). TryHackMe, <https://tryhackme.com> (Accessed June 3, 2025).